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**H. G. WELLS VA OLDOUS HAKLINING ILMIY FANTASTIKA JANRIGA QO'SHGAN
HISSASI VA UNING QISQACHA TAHLILI** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7038132>**ANNOTATSIYA**

Jahon adabiyotida ilmiy fantastikaning adabiy janr sifatida tutgan o'rni o'ziga xos ahamiyatga ega. Ingliz adabiyotida bu borada so'z borganda Gerbert Uels va Oldos Haksli ijodi va ularning bu janrda yaratgan asarlarini ta'kidlab o'tish zarur. Ushbu maqolada ilmiy fantastika janri va xususan Gerbert Uels va Oldos Hakslining bu janrga qoshgan hissasi va asarlarning badiiy qiymati haqida soz boradi. Bu borada so'z borar ekan mavzuning tadqiqot obyekti sifatida bu ikki ijodkor asarlari va ular yashagan davr va ijtimoiy muhit e'tibor markazida bo'ladi.

Tayanch so'zlar: adabiyot, jamiyat, ilmiy fantastika, janr, vaqt mashinasi, ko'rinmas odam

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**SHORT ANALYSIS OF H. G. WELLS AND ALDOUS HUXLEY'S CONTRIBUTION TO
THE SCIENCE FICTION GENRE****ANNOTATION**

The role of science fiction as a literary genre in the world literature is of special importance. When talking about this in English literature, it is necessary to emphasize the works of Herbert Wells and Aldous Huxley and their works in this genre. This article will discuss the science fiction genre and, in particular, the contribution of Herbert Wells and Aldous Huxley to this genre and the literary value of the works. While talking about the topic, the works of these two artists and the period and social environment in which they lived will be in the center of attention as the research object of the topic.

Key words: literature, society, science fiction, genre, The Time Machine, The Invisible Man

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КРАТКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ВКЛАДА ГЕРБЕРТА УЭЛЛСА И ОЛДОСА ХАКСЛИ В ЖАНР НАУЧНОЙ ФАНТАСТИКИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Роль научной фантастики как литературного жанра в мировой литературе имеет особое значение. Говоря об этом в англоязычной литературе, необходимо выделить творчество Герберта Уэллса и Олдоса Хаксли и их произведения в этом жанре. В данной статье рассматривается жанр научной фантастики, и в частности вклад Герберта Уэллса и Олдоса Хаксли в это жанр и художественная ценность произведений. При разговоре на эту тему в центре внимания как объект исследования темы будут произведения этих двух художников, а также период и социальная среда, в которой они жили.

Ключевые слова: литература, общество, фантастика, жанр, машина времени, человек-невидимка.

A SHORT ANALYSIS OF H. G. WELLS AND ALDOUS HUXLEY'S CONTRIBUTION TO THE SCIENCE FICTION GENRE

Science Fiction is that class of prose narrative treating of a situation that could not arise in the world we know, but which is hypothesized on the basis of some innovation in science or technology, or pseudo-technology, whether human or extra-terrestrial in origin. (Brooke-Rose, 1983:72)

Science fiction has come a long way since its early days, when Isaac Asimov defined it as "that branch of literature which is concerned with the impact of scientific advance upon human beings" (*Modern Science Fiction*, 1953). By the 70s, the genre of science-based ideas had grown; it wasn't just concerned with science, but with consequences. It asked "what if?" What if a world existed in which this or that were true? Pamela Sargent dubbed it "the literature of ideas."

Science fiction is often said to inspire a "sense of wonder." Science fiction editor and critic David Hartwell wrote: "Science fiction's appeal lies in combination of the rational, the believable, with the miraculous. It is an appeal to the sense of wonder." Carl Sagan said: "One of the great benefits of science fiction is that it can convey bits and pieces, hints, and phrases, of knowledge unknown or inaccessible to the reader . . . works you ponder over as the water is running out of the bathtub or as you walk through the woods in an early winter snowfall."

Nobody can deny that science fiction is one of the very oldest literary genres, even if we live in the postmodern period. Science fiction authors produced such science fiction books throughout the latter half of the nineteenth century and during the first half of the twentieth century, but they differed greatly from one another in every way. Jules Verne, H.G. Wells, Fitz-James O'Brien, Aldous Huxley, Robert Louis Stevenson, Percival Lawrence Lowell, Hugo Gernback, H. Keller, J.G. Ballard, Brian Wilson Aldiss, Robert A. Heinlein, William Gibson, Michael Crichton, Isaac Asimov, and others are among the authors represented. In their writings, they all specifically and blatantly investigated scientific, social, futuristic, political, philosophical, and psychological topics.

The two most notable and well-known authors in this genre, Herbert George Wells (1866–1946) and Aldous Leonard Huxley (1894–1963), attempted to depict the world of the future using scientific fancies and social realities. The adage "Mary Shelly planned the flag of science fiction on the new territories, but H. G. Wells explored them, populated them, and developed them" about H. G. Wells is accurate. (1977:15 Scholes)

It was written by H.G. Wells and is the first work to address the concept of time travel. His theories gained popularity as he introduced the idea of time travel, and they also highlighted the intensity and profundity of science fiction. He depicts the voyage of a time traveler in the future using "time" as the fourth dimension. Even after 117 years, many of the topics and ideas covered in H. G. Wells' *The Time Machine* are still relevant today. This novella exposes the effects of Darwinism and raises important questions about society, and especially about the society of the future. With the aid of his finest use of fantasy, H. G. Wells makes an effort to convey the image of a future civilization.

Every element used in the novella has been handled logically. Even the future time frame that the novel's protagonist experiences makes sense. Wells adopts this strategy because, during his time period, several writers predicted a future that would be destroyed in around a million years. Wells has

used this idea to create the backdrop for his fictional works. In fact, H. G. Wells "employs bogus scientific innovations to generate fake settings in order to analyze his own surroundings" in this socially and politically aware work of fiction. (Spek, 2000:38)

The idea of "aliens" from other planets was first established by H. G. Wells, and authors following him almost exclusively portrayed these aliens as hostile, evil monsters who were single-mindedly committed to conquest and destruction. Miller (2002):38–40

Another well-known English author, besides Wells, has effectively carved out a place for himself in the canon of science fiction authors. Without studying and analyzing the work of Aldous Leonard Huxley (1894–1963), a contemporary science fiction author to Herbert George Wells and well-known for his books and poetry, the circle of science fiction seems to be incomplete. He was the grandson of English biologist Thomas Henry Huxley, who was well-known for supporting Charles Darwin's theory of evolution. He began his literary career by satirizing society in his work. Huxley is most known to science fiction authors for his masterwork, a fantastic dystopian novel called *Brave New World* (1932).

Regarding various facets of society, he maintained a wide range of ideas and points of view. The fundamental premise of his *Brave New World* is that a wanted or anticipated human being is generated in an artificially fertilized egg by the artificial fertilization of an ovum from four females and a spermatozoon from a male; an embryo is predetermined, and a newborn is trained. He made an effort to integrate recognizable human elements into an unknown futuristic technocratic society. Additionally, he produced several insightful, thought-provoking, religious, philosophical, social, and intriguing works. He authored his first unpublished novel, *Crome Yellow*, when he was seventeen years old (1921).

His other books include *Island* (1962), *Eyeless in Gaza* (1936), *After Many a Summer* (1939), *Time Must Have a Stop* (1944), *Those Barren Leaves* (1925), *Point Counter Point* (1928), *Antic Hay* (1923), *Eyeless in Gaza*, *Ape and Essence*, and *Point Counter Point*. In addition to it, he also authored children's novels, screenplays, plays, essay collections, and poetry collections. In his work, he used a wide variety of subjects, genres, and approaches.

Aldous Huxley began as an *enfant terrible* and finished as a sage, as Robert E. Kuehn correctly observes in the preface to his collection of critical writings about him. It has also been thought about how his writing style and subjects have altered and been identified as unique from his first novel, *Crome Yellow*, through his last novels, *Island* (Kuehn, 1974:01).

The best way for any writer to express themselves is via their work, and Aldous Huxley is no exception to this rule. His writing style altered over the course of his whole career, and in this flow, he included his utopian beliefs as the thoughts predicting the future. In his book *Brave New World*, he attempted to depict a utopian future and the results of an irresponsible human race. Aldous Huxley expressed the picture of the future in *Ape and Essence* (1948), however he did it in a rather disorganized way.

In his prediction, he described how people will live in the twenty-second century. He also said that in the twenty-second century humans may have superior technology and act like wild animals. The well-formed civilization was detailed in his final book, *Island* (1962). He discussed his proposal to combine eastern philosophy and western science to develop a utopia on Earth. Aldous Huxley depicts a dreadful future that is nothing more than the inevitable result of our current society's trends.

He strongly attacks on future society on the grounds of its progressivism in the field of science and technology but at the same moment there is destruction and eradication of religion, art and sex. He put the dystopian frame of future society to which he wished to call as the technocratic hell. Mark Hillegas commented on the same as: He was against utopia not only because it would mechanize human life but because it would give abundance and leisure to everyone, making these no longer the special privilege of people like himself. (Hillegas, 1974:120)

Science fiction's rapid rise in popularity during the first half of the 20th century was closely tied to the popular respect paid to science at that time, as well as the rapid pace of technological innovation and new inventions. Science fiction has often predicted scientific and technological progress. Some works predict that new inventions and progress will tend to improve life and society,

for instance the stories of Arthur C. Clarke and *Star Trek*. Others, such as H.G.Wells's *The Time Machine* and Aldous Huxley's *Brave New World*, warn about possible negative consequences.

To sum up, it is important to note that the current society has undergone significant transformation. It is apparent that science and technology's advancement and growth are the only factors contributing to these dynamic and extreme developments. However, after learning about the history of science fiction, its different meanings, and the contributions of H. G.Wells and Aldous Huxley, one could see that these works are in some ways contributing to the progressive in the area of science and technology.

It won't be wrong if one says that somewhere behind all this scientific and technological progress there is science fiction and upto a great extent it is absolutely acceptable and the contribution of the science fiction writers.

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